

THE PROJECT

Although fungi are vital for our ecosystems, they are still often overlooked in conservation policy and practice across Europe. This neglect is no longer acceptable. In FunDive (EU Biodiversa+), we work to put fungal biodiversity on the map to improve protection efforts. Will you join us?

WHAT ARE ALIEN MUSHROOMS?

So-called alien species have been moved beyond their natural geographical range by humans. Various non-native mushroom species have been introduced in several European regions, either intentionally (for example, commercial species) or accidentally (for instance, introduced as spores carried on shoes). Once introduced, some species will persist and spread.

WHY REGISTER YOUR OBSERVATIONS?

Many non-native mushrooms are now spreading across Europe and we don't yet know what the consequences will be. Could they displace native species and disrupt local ecosystems?

If you share your observations on iNaturalist, you will be helping to track their spread. We will use the data for scientific research and management decisions on alien mushrooms. What's more, you will be amazed by what you see. Some of our target species truly look out of this world!

FunDive

EYES ON ALIEN MUSHROOMS

A citizen science campaign tracking non-native mushrooms across Europe.

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Back photo: © Susana P. Cunha
FunDive Link: <https://fun-dive.eu/en/get-involved/>

TARGET SPECIES

© Federico Calleda

Aureoboletus projectellus

© rowesnata

Pleurotus citrinopileatus
(Golden Oyster Mushroom)

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Pleurotus citrinopileatus
(Golden Oyster Mushroom)

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Favolaschia claudopus
(Orange Pore Fungus)

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Leratiomyces ceres
(Chip Cherries)

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Stereum illudens

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Clathrus archeri
(Devil's-Fingers)

HOW TO GET STARTED?

- Sign up for an iNaturalist account on the app or website (www.inaturalist.org), and join the FunDive project <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/eyes-on-alien-mushrooms>
- If your country has a local iNaturalist network, remember to join the appropriate iNaturalist affiliation.
- Capture photos of non-native mushrooms around you, preferably with GPS turned on to automatically record the date and location of the mushroom. Upload your photos, along the location and date to iNaturalist.
- Join the conversation on alien mushrooms with other enthusiasts across Europe using the comments on iNaturalist.
- Need more help? Visit <https://help.inaturalist.org/en/support>

WHAT TO DO?

- Photographs should be in focus and well lit, but avoid using flash.
- Make sure you can see details clearly and use an object for scale, such as a dark coin.
- Capture all relevant morphological features such as the cap and its underside (surface of the pores/gills), and the stem, including the base. Document any colour changes or exudation after cutting.
- Show the mushroom *in situ* and include its host or substrate (i.e. if it grows under a specific tree, show leaves next to the mushroom, or take a separate photograph).
- Photograph the spores if you come across a deposit on leaves or other mushrooms.
- Add details that cannot be captured in the photographs to the notes section, such as any distinctive odour, taste or texture.

WANT TO GO THE EXTRA MILE?

- Quick hot air dry your finding and store it in a small hermetic plastic bag. We might ask you to send it for DNA sequencing!